

SPR

H₂N-LCB1

File: MI_NiNTA_f1

Sample: LS

AcLCB1

File: MI_NiNTA_f2

Sample: LCB1

(B_p-R_p)PNA

File: MI_NiNTA_f3

Sample: E

- 1) antiRBD antibody (CR3022 – InvivoGen, vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f1
Sample: RBD-Antibody
- 2) R(-C) and B(-C) peptides (equimolar up to 2 μM vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f1
Sample: RB
- 3) DMSO (up to 0.8% vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f2
Sample: DMSO
- 4) (R-R) homodimer (up to 2 μM vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f2
Sample: rCrC
- 5) (B-R) (up to 2 μM vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f2
Sample: rCbC
- 6) B(-C)_{PNA} and R(-C)_{PNA} (equimolar, annealed vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f3
Sample: rPNA bPNA A
- 7) B(-C)_{PNA} and R(-C)_{PNA} (equimolar, non-annealed vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f3
Sample: rPNA bPNA nA
- 8) B_{PNA} and R_{PNA} (equimolar, annealed vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f4
Sample: rC PNA bC PNA A
- 9) (B-R)_{PNA} (vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f5
Sample: rC PNA bC PNA r2 II
- 10) (B-R)_{PEG1PNA} (vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f6
Sample: rCbC PNA PEG1
- 11) (B-R)_{PEG2PNA} (vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f6
Sample: rCbC PNA PEG2
- 12) (B-R)_{PEG3} (vs RBD on NiNTA chip)
File: MI_NiNTA_f4
Sample: B
- 13) (B_CR_C)_{PEG2PNA} (vs RBD on NiNTA chip)
File: MI_NiNTA_f5
Sample: RCm-BCm
- 14) AcLCB1 (vs RBD on CM5 chip)
File: MI_CM5_f6
Sample: LCB1

LC-MS

Screening heterodimer formation experiment:

R0 – no additive, 25 °C, 50 μM

O1 – no additive, 25 °C, 100 μM

O2 – no additive, 37 °C, 100 μM

O3– GSSG, 25 °C, 100 μM

O4– Cu(II), 25 °C, 100 μM

For characterisation the filename correspond to chromatogram label in the SI.